

Arts

THE RISE OF DIGITAL ART

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Abstract

The medium of digital art has existed for over a hundred years, but it's only now that it's getting the spotlight. Technology is a means of actions. Like a pencil or a canvas. Digital technology is the latest of a series of tool used by artist. According to digital artist "To me, my mouse, keyboard and text editor or DAW are what a paint brush palette and canvas would be to a painter.

Traditional art workflow can be emulated in the digital domain or be augmented with digital practices. Digital art is defined as artistic works that utilized digital technology as part of the creative process.

Keywords: Digital; Technology; Art; Computer; Creative.

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1. Introduction

Since the origin of humankind, people have been fighting to seize what they experience and share it with others, they have been using whatever they had available at the time. First clay, then colourful clay, charcoal, wood, sharp animal bone, then special pigments mixed with water or oil, they've been made with pencils and inks on paper painting with paints on canvas sculpting in clay, wood, ivory, and stone, the material world offers a heap of possibilities for the creative judgment of a man.

Yet, today something new and amazing, a kind of a new world the digital globe.

The digital world is not bound by any limitation of the material world. We can take all the colours, the human eye can take in. We can change their vividness and brightness, we can combine them and erase without a buck.

As technologies expand, the possibilities for art expand.

2. Digital Art

Digital artwork is an aesthetic work or drill that utilizes digital technology as an indispensable component of the creation or presentation process. Since the 1970s, several names have been applied to identify the process, including computer art and multimedia art, and digital art is itself placed under the larger umbrella term new media artwork.

An art in which computer technology is used in a broad diversity of ways to make distinctive works. Digital Painting is painting, drawing, or illustration created using a Digital application. It is not a form of Art movement or an Art like pop art or modern art. It exclusively involves creating art by using computers and specific type of applications called Vector Applications to create art.

While this may seem like a niche interest digital art actually spans an incredibly broad spectrum of medium that range from animation and digital painting to 3d printed sculpture and video etc. Many believe that digital art often consists of solely graphic design and that it doesn't go very far beyond that. However, digital art has existed for many years and is a term that expands to fit in new ideas as fast as artist can come up with them.

Digital and computer art became popularly recognized in the 1950's when pioneers of the subject used oscilloscopes.

3. The History of Computer Art

Creative persons first initiate experimenting with computers in the 1950s. The first computer art show, Computer Generated Pictures, was halted at the Howard Wise Gallery in New York. Another large-scale exhibition of computer artwork - Cybernetic Serendipity - was arrested in London in 1969 at the Institute of Contemporary Arts. At this stage most of the artwork produced (called Digital or Cybernetic art) was graphical and emphasized geometric shapes in different random combinations. Not particularly exciting today, but groundbreaking in their time.

4. 1970s

The next development came in the 1970s with the acquaintance of the light pen or stylus. This was a digital pen that allowed the user to move and juxtapose items around on the computer monitor, permitting more flexibility (today they are frequently employed with digital personal organizers). Well known creative persons like David Hockney (b. 1937) and the British painter and college creative person Richard Hamilton (1922-2011) experimented with the engineering. (Later in 1992, Hamilton applied the Quantel Paintbox system to manipulate his 1956 collage Just What is it That Makes Today's Homes So discontinuous, So Appealing. Then, as to reflect the present-day era.)

But computer art doesn't merely refer to images created on screen. It likewise refers to compositions of art works where computer technology was used somewhere in their creative process. For example the creative person Harold Cohen (b. 1928) produces his own computer programs to randomly get a form of abstract drawings, which he then blows up and colours by hand. Plans have also been employed to check the movement of Kinetic sculptures.

As technology and computer software has sprung up, the possibilities of computer art continued to inflate. The Copy Art movement (c. 1976-86), which sprang up in the United States and spread to Europe (via Live Prins in the Netherlands, Jurgen O Olbrich in Germany, and Bruno Munari in Italy) gave a boost to computerized art forms. The coming of the inkjet printer in 1976 made it easier for creative persons to make Giclee prints of their deeds. At the same time, French creative persons, including Jean Mathiaut, Philippe Jeantet, Jean-Pierre Garrault, and Daniel Cabanis, experimented with flatbed copying, picture processing, video integration and digital art.

5. 1980, 1990

In the 1980s and 1990s the term started to encompass interactive environment that placed both viewer and creative person at the interface between the literal and practical worlds. The creative person focused on manipulating imagery with the supporter of computer software tools. Thus new companies like Adobe launched in 1982 created easy to use creative person software, like their vector drawing program Adobe illustrator. It is however one of the primary programs used by computer creative persons today. The digitizers manipulating of photographs with software programs like Photoshop have created a young breed of exciting contemporary creative persons such as Andreas Gursky (1955) and Jeff Wall (1946).

In Japan, a diminished group of computer creative person called Dumb type, founded in Kyoto in the mid 1980s, specializes in the production of installations, featuring music, dance, dramatic art, television and photography, whose imagery totally immersed the viewer.

During the 1980s postmodernist architects like Frank O. Gehry developed Deconstructivism, a kind of anti Euclidean style of avant garde architecture, employing computer software derived from the aerospace manufacture. This 3-d form of computer art is illustrated in buildings like the Guggenheim Museum In Bilbo (1991-97)

Developments in hardware have also influenced the industry. Many creative persons in 21st century use Apple Computer products - note the popularity of the iPad and touch screen technology, which makes computer imagery more accessible than ever.

6. Conclusion

We live in a century dominated by technology innovation, art itself has been offered new creative horizons, but these new advantages have not been considered so beneficial for the art by some Conservative art lovers who believe that if the art is not created using traditional tools (pen, oil water color etc.) that art cannot be considered true art.

Using a computer to make art is so great that I do not have to buy those materials like paint, brushes, and canvas this save a huge sum of money and time.

These two thoughts are given by a traditional artist and a digital artist. They both think that the medium that they were use is better than another.

Today creative persons have so many options available, and I believe we shouldn't limit ourselves to the old, classic definition of art. I use traditional ink liners in my traditional sketchbook to sketch and study, because I like to draw while half-laying on my couch. I paint digitally in SketchBook Pro because I love the possibility to use all the colours and brushes without the pressure to get everything right the first time. And I love that I live in the times when my art can be shared with thousands of people in a digital form.

Whether it is digital art or traditional art they are both art. The differences between the two are the media you use. I once read an article on the internet that said "Teaching an creative person how to use a computer is easier than teaching a computer user how to be an creative person". Before I switched to digital medium I had to learn composition, the human figure, perspective etc., for years with a pencil. Because I have knowledge how to use traditional media the transition was easy. I bought my WACOM BAMBOO way back in 2008 and it took me six months before I considered myself a digital illustrator. I still sketch on paper with a pencil when delivering rough thumbnails. Traditional art is here to stay even if computers will become more advanced.

Digital art also includes new art experience when it comes to exhibitions plays , ballet , and opera virtual reality has become the main tool used to shape those experience.

Many national museums are trying to take this technological turn by digitazing their collection and archives in 3D.

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